

Institute of Discourse Perspective

2nd International Conference

Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics & Impact

The phenomenal speaker presents this research in 2nd International Conference Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held on 25-27 April 2025 at Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. The Conference Abstract is published on behalf of the decision of acceptance and approval of aforesaid Conference Organizing Committee.

Correspondence:

Hafiz Sajid Iqbal PhD, Chair of Organizing Committee, 2nd International Conference, Institute of discourse Perspectives, E.:
conferences.idp@gmail.com |
www.idpinstitute.com | +92 300 496 9385
| +92 333 4060783

Conference Secretariat: Fayaz Khan

Jadoon, Dept. of Islamic Studies, University of Management and Technology C-II, Johar Town, Lahore Pakistan. T.: +92 42 35212801-10,
<https://www.umat.edu.pk>

Citation:

Hafiz Muhammad Haroon Alavi, 2nd International Conference, Syed Maududi's Thought: Dynamics &, held in Al-Razi Hall, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. Vol. 12 (2025). p. 63-64.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information is available at the end of the article.

Conference Abstract

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE MUSLIM UMMAH: A STUDY ON THE CONCEPT OF "TESTIMONY TO THE TRUTH" IN SYED MAUDUDI'S THOUGHT

Hafiz Muhammad Haroon Alavi

PhD Scholar, Islamic Thought and Civilization at University of Management and Technology, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Ethics approval and consent to participate: No ethical approval needed for this research work.

Consent for publication: Author is agreed to submit this abstract for publication in this research journal.

Availability of data and materials: The information and data collected and/ or incorporated in this study is included in this manuscript.

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the core concept of *Shahādāt al-Ḥaqq* (Bearing Witness to the Truth) as formulated in the thought of Syed Abul A'la Maududi, and its Immediate consequences for the Missions and mandates of the Ummah. Maududi highlighted that the Muslim Ummah is theologically mandated to serve as a witness to society by conveying and personifying the message of Islam—this constituting its foremost responsibility and existential goal. The analysis explores how Maududi theorized the responsibilities of Muslims, particularly their unified task to administer justice, propagate the truth, and serve as ethical models. Fundamental to this is the distinction between verbal testimony (preaching and declaration of faith) and practical testimony (living by Islamic values). Maududi emphasized that both aspects are essential to the fulfillment of testimony and the fulfillment of the argument upon humankind. The study additionally examines the significance of testimony in Maududi's writings, and the severe outcomes of abandoning this responsibility. Neglect in this aspect results in responsibility, both in this world and in the Hereafter, including the punishment for suppressing the truth (*kitmān al-ḥaqq*). Through a critical evaluation of the Muslim Ummah's current verbal and practical testimony, the research contemplates How well modern conduct corresponds with Maududi's vision. The discoveries emphasize the urgent need for revival and reformation in light of his thought to regain the Ummah's ordained international mission.

Keywords: Syed Maududi, Muslim Ummah, Roles and Responsibilities, Importance of testimony to the truth.

© 2025The Author(s). This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 license.

You are free to:

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

No additional restrictions

You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits